

ABOUT ENGLISH ANTONYMS

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Abstract: *this article provides information on English antonyms. in addition, the types of antonyms and their use in speech structure are analyzed.*

Key words: *English antonyms, polysemantic words, parts of speech, category.*

We use the term antonyms to indicate words of the same category of parts of speech which have contrasting meanings, such as hot – cold, light – dark, happiness – sorrow, to accept – to reject, up – down.

If synonyms form whole, often numerous groups, antonyms are usually believed to appear in pairs. Yet, this is not quite true in reality. For instance, the adjective cold may be said to have warm for its second antonym, and sorrow may be very well contrasted with gaiety.

On the other hand, a polysemantic word may have an antonym (or several antonyms) for each of its meanings. So, the adjective *dull* has the antonyms interesting, amusing, entertaining for its meaning of “deficient in interest”, *clever, bright, capable* for its meaning of “deficient in intellect”, and *active* for the meaning of “deficient in activity”.

Antonymy is not evenly distributed among the categories of parts of speech. Most antonyms are adjectives which is natural because qualitative characteristics are easily compared and contrasted: high – low, wide – narrow, strong – weak, old – young, friendly – hostile.

Verbs take the second place, so far as antonymy is concerned. Yet, verbal pairs are fewer in number. Here are some of them: to lose – to find, to live – to die, to open – to close, to weep – to laugh.

Antonymic adverbs can be subdivided into two groups; a) adverbs derived from adjectives: warmly – coldly, merrily – sadly, loudly – softly; b) adverbs proper: now – then, here – there, ever – never, up – down, in – out.

4 Types of Antonyms

The main types of antonyms in the English language are:

1. **Auto-antonym:** An auto-antonym is a word that has two meanings, including one with an opposite meaning. It has several different names, including “contronym” and “Janus word.” Examples of auto-antonyms include “bound,” “dust,” “consult,” and “fast”.

2. **Complementary antonyms:** Also known as direct antonyms or contradictory antonyms, complementary antonyms are related words that are absolute opposites.

They exist independently from one another and do not need the other term to exist. Examples of complementary antonyms include “want and day” and “inhale and exhale”.

3. **Converse antonyms:** Converse antonyms, or relational antonyms, are closely related words that can't exist without each other. For example, “near” and “far” are converse antonyms because an object can't be near without measuring it with something far away.

4. **Graded:** Graded antonyms show variations or grades between words with similar meanings. While “pleased”, “gratified”, “overjoyed”, and “content” all have a relational connection to “happy”, each has a different definition

Not so many years ago antonymy was not universally accepted as a linguistic problem, and the opposition within antonymic pairs was regarded as purely logical and finding no reflection in the semantic structures of these words. The contrast between heat and cold or big and small, said most scholars, is the contrast of things opposed by their very nature. When we were dealing with the problem of synonymy, we emphasized the fact that both the identity and differentiations in words called synonyms can be said to be encoded within their semantic structures. Can the same be said about antonyms? Modern research in the field of antonymy gives a positive answer to this question. Nowadays most scholars agree that in the semantic structures of all words, which regularly occur in antonymic pairs, a special antonymic connotation can be singled out. We are so used to coming across hot and cold together, in the same contexts, that even when we find hot alone, we cannot help subconsciously registering it as not cold, that is, contrast it to its missing antonym. The word possesses its full meaning for us not only due to its direct associations but also because we subconsciously oppose it to its antonym, with which it is regularly used, in this case to hot. Therefore, it is reasonable to suggest that the semantic structure of hot can be said to include the antonymic connotation of “not cold”, and the semantic structure of enemy the connotation of “not a friend”.

It should be stressed once more that we are speaking only about those antonyms which are characterized by common occurrences, that is, which are regularly used in pairs. When two words frequently occur side by side in numerous contexts, subtle and complex associations between them are not at all unusual. These associations are naturally reflected in the word's semantic structures. Antonymic connotations are a special case of such “reflected associations”.

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